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ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF COMMUNTING AND BOARDING ISLET ADOLESCENT STUDENTS ENROLLED AT BANTAYAN NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL IN BANTAYAN ISLAND, CEBU (S.Y 2008-2009 to S.Y 2011-2012)

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THESIS ABSTRACT

The primary purpose of this study is to determine the relationship between the academic performance of the commuting and boarding islet students. To do this, the periodical test results of 30 commuting and 30 boarding islet adolescent high school students of the Bantayan National High School (Bantayan Island, Province of Cebu) were analyzed. To guide the analysis, the following research questions and hypothesis were drawn: What is the economic status of the parents of commuting students? and What is the economic status of the parents of boarding students? Hypothesis revealed that there is no significant difference between the means of the academic performance of commuting and boarding students at 5% significant level. With regards to the issues raised in the research questions, it has been found out that the parents of the commuting students are generally fishermen (96.67%) with an average monthly income of only P 3, 736.67. Whereas, for the parents of the boarding students, eighty-three point thirty-three (83.33%) percent are fishermen with a monthly income of P 3, 948.28. The average monthly income of the islet parent is P 3, 842.48. With regards to the null hypothesis of no difference between their academic mean performance, the t-test shows that the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a difference between their mean academic performances in favor of the boarding students, that is 26.48 for boarding students and 24.34 for commuting students. The percentage difference is 8.79% based on the mean of the commuting students. The conclusions can be drawn from this study (1) the overall average monthly income of P 3, 842.43 is beyond imagination for them to be able to live decently. They need livelihood assistance to improve their living conditions (2) the fact that even with their meager monthly income they were still able to send their children to school, shows their strong belief of what good education can do to change their economic situation in life and (3) the islet students staying in boarding houses generally show a significantly higher academic performance than those students commuting daily to school.

Keywords: students' academic performance, adolescent, islet, commuting islet student, boarding islet student

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